

Assessing Pancreatic Fat Content and Postpancreatectomy Outcomes: The Significance of the Pancreatic Attenuation Index

Sanul Shahi K. Salim¹, Tsella Lachungpa²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Radiology, Sikkim Manipal Institute of Medical Sciences, Sikkim, India

²Associate Professor, Department of Radiology, Sikkim Manipal Institute of Medical Sciences, Sikkim, India

Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 25-07-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Sanul Shahi K. Salim

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

This study investigates the predictive value of the Pancreatic Attenuation Index (PAI) in assessing post-pancreatectomy outcomes and its significance in preoperative risk assessment. A prospective cohort analysis was conducted on 12 patients undergoing elective pancreatectomy at a single institution over one year. Preoperative PAI measurements were correlated with postoperative complications and hospital stay duration. The results demonstrate a significant association between lower PAI scores and increased postoperative complications, particularly pancreatic fistula, as well as prolonged hospital stays. These findings suggest that PAI offers valuable insights into pancreatic health and prognosis, informing surgical decision-making and optimizing patient care pathways. Further research is warranted to validate these findings in larger cohorts and elucidate underlying mechanisms.

Keywords: Pancreatic Attenuation Index, pancreatectomy, pancreatic fat content, postoperative outcomes, surgical risk assessment.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

The assessment of pancreatic fat content and its implications for post-pancreatectomy outcomes represents a critical frontier in medical research. Pancreatic steatosis, characterized by excessive fat accumulation within the pancreas, has garnered increasing attention due to its association with various metabolic disorders and surgical complications. In this context, the Pancreatic Attenuation Index (PAI) emerges as a promising tool for quantifying pancreatic fat content and evaluating its clinical relevance [1,2].

Over the years, advancements in imaging techniques, particularly computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), have enabled precise evaluation of pancreatic fat infiltration [3]. The PAI, derived from CT scans, measures the attenuation of pancreatic tissue, providing a quantitative assessment of fat content. Its utilization in clinical practice holds significant potential for refining risk stratification and guiding therapeutic interventions in patients undergoing pancreatectomy [4,5].

The study prepares for a detailed discussion of the Pancreatic Attenuation Index's significance in pancreatic fat content assessment and post-pancreatectomy outcomes. This review synthesizes current research and clinical applications to

demonstrate PAI's diagnostic and prognostic value in pancreatic disease management. This study evaluates the Pancreatic Attenuation Index (PAI) for pancreatic fat content and post-pancreatectomy outcomes. Our study investigates whether PAI measurements may be integrated into clinical practice to improve risk stratification and perioperative care in pancreatectomy patients. This research intends to advance the discipline and promote evidence-based patient care by understanding PAI assessment's larger significance in pancreatic diseases and metabolic syndrome.

Material and Methodology

Study Design: This study was designed as a prospective cohort analysis to explore the relationship between pancreatic fat content, as quantified by the Pancreatic Attenuation Index (PAI), and post-pancreatectomy outcomes. The assessment focused on determining how preoperative PAI values correlate with surgical results and recovery parameters.

Setting: The research was conducted at the Sikkim Manipal Institute of Medical Sciences. This facility was chosen due to its comprehensive medical imaging technology and specialized surgical units that routinely perform pancreatic surgeries.

Participants: A total of 12 patients scheduled for elective pancreatectomy between April 16, 2022, and April 15, 2023, were enrolled in the study. Inclusion criteria were adult patients (aged 18 and older) diagnosed with conditions necessitating pancreatectomy. Exclusion criteria included patients with previous pancreatic surgery, chronic pancreatitis, or any contraindication to surgery as per the institution's guidelines.

Data Collection: Preoperative assessment included a detailed clinical evaluation, laboratory tests, and CT scans of the abdomen to calculate the PAI. The PAI was measured by radiologists blinded to the study's clinical objectives, utilizing the CT scan images to calculate the ratio of pancreatic parenchymal attenuation compared to the spleen. Postoperative outcomes assessed included duration of hospital stay, postoperative complications such as pancreatic fistula, and overall mortality and morbidity rates within 30 days post-surgery.

Sample Size Justification: The sample size of 12 was determined based on the feasibility of enrolling eligible patients within the one-year study period at the institution, considering the relatively low frequency of pancreatectomy procedures. This sample size is adequate for preliminary analysis and hypothesis generation, with plans for future studies to validate findings in a larger cohort.

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize patient demographics, PAI scores, and postoperative outcomes. Correlations between PAI scores and postoperative outcomes will be analyzed using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient. Additional regression analyses may be conducted to adjust for potential confounders. A p-value of less than 0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

Results

Participant Characteristics: The study enrolled 12 patients (7 males and 5 females) with an average age of 58 years (range 43-71 years). The primary indications for pancreatectomy were pancreatic adenocarcinoma in 6 patients, neuroendocrine tumors in 4 patients, and cystic neoplasms in 2 patients.

Pancreatic Attenuation Index (PAI) Measurements: The PAI was calculated for each patient based on preoperative CT scans. The mean PAI was 8.4 Hounsfield Units (HU), with a range from 6.2 HU to 10.6 HU. There was a significant negative correlation between PAI and the presence of fat within the pancreatic parenchyma, indicating higher fat content with lower attenuation values.

Postoperative Outcomes: The average hospital stay post-pancreatectomy was 11 days (range 8-15 days). Complications occurred in 5 patients (41.7%), including pancreatic fistula in 3 patients

(25%) and postoperative infections in 2 patients (16.7%). There was no mortality observed within 30 days post-surgery.

Correlation Analysis: Spearman's rank correlation analysis showed a statistically significant correlation between lower PAI scores and increased postoperative complications ($\rho = -0.68$, $p = 0.012$). Specifically, patients with a PAI less than 7.5 HU had a higher rate of pancreatic fistula. Additionally, a lower PAI was associated with prolonged hospital stays.

Regression Analysis: Regression analysis indicated that after adjusting for age, sex, and type of tumor, PAI remained a significant predictor of postoperative complications (odds ratio = 0.62, 95% confidence interval = 0.41-0.89, $p = 0.009$).

The results of this study suggest that a lower Pancreatic Attenuation Index, indicative of higher pancreatic fat content, is associated with an increased risk of postoperative complications, particularly pancreatic fistula, and prolonged hospital stays. These findings underscore the importance of considering pancreatic fat content as a significant factor in preoperative planning and risk stratification for patients undergoing pancreatectomy.

Discussion

The findings of this study shed light on the significance of the Pancreatic Attenuation Index (PAI) in predicting post-pancreatectomy outcomes and highlight its potential role as a valuable tool in preoperative risk assessment. By evaluating pancreatic fat content through PAI measurements, this study aimed to elucidate its association with postoperative complications and hospital stay duration [6].

The results revealed a notable correlation between lower PAI scores, indicative of higher pancreatic fat content, and increased postoperative complications, particularly pancreatic fistula [7]. This association suggests that the presence of excessive fat within the pancreatic parenchyma may predispose patients to surgical challenges and subsequent complications. Additionally, patients with lower PAI scores exhibited prolonged hospital stays, indicating a potential impact on overall recovery and healthcare resource utilization [8].

The implications of these findings are twofold. Firstly, preoperative assessment of pancreatic fat content using PAI could serve as a valuable prognostic indicator for surgical planning. Surgeons may use this information to tailor their approach, anticipate potential intraoperative difficulties, and implement preventive measures to mitigate postoperative complications [9]. Secondly, PAI could aid in patient selection and risk stratification, enabling healthcare providers to

identify individuals at higher risk of adverse outcomes and allocate resources accordingly, thereby optimizing patient care pathways [10].

Despite its contributions, this study has several limitations. The small sample size limits the generalizability of the findings, necessitating

validation in larger cohorts. Additionally, the single-center nature of the study introduces potential biases and limits external validity. Future research should aim to address these limitations by conducting multicenter studies with larger and more diverse patient populations [11].

Table 1: This tabular representation summarizes the participant characteristics, PAI measurements, postoperative outcomes, correlation analysis, and regression analysis findings from the study.

Parameter	Value
Total Participants	12
Gender Distribution	7 males, 5 females
Average Age	58 years
Age Range	43-71 years
Indications for Surgery	- Pancreatic adenocarcinoma: 6 - Neuroendocrine tumors: 4 - Cystic neoplasms: 2
PAI (Hounsfield Units)	Mean: 8.4, Range: 6.2-10.6
PAI Correlation with Fat	Negative (higher fat, lower PAI)
Average Hospital Stay	11 days
Hospital Stay Range	8-15 days
Complications Rate	41.7%
Specific Complications	- Pancreatic fistula: 25% - Postoperative infections: 16.7%
30-day Mortality	0%
Spearman's rho (PAI vs Complications)	-0.68
Significance (p-value)	0.012
Regression Analysis Odds Ratio	0.62
95% Confidence Interval	0.41-0.89
Regression Analysis p-value	0.009

Furthermore, while the study focused on the association between PAI and postoperative outcomes, the underlying mechanisms linking pancreatic fat content to surgical complications remain unclear. Future investigations could explore the pathophysiological pathways involved, including the impact of pancreatic steatosis on tissue quality, perfusion, and healing processes.

Conclusion

Our study describes the potential of the Pancreatic Attenuation Index (PAI) as a valuable preoperative tool for risk assessment and prognostication in patients undergoing pancreatectomy. Through a prospective cohort analysis of 12 patients, we observed a significant correlation between lower PAI scores and increased postoperative complications, particularly pancreatic fistula, as well as prolonged hospital stays. These findings highlight the importance of considering pancreatic fat content in surgical planning, enabling surgeons to anticipate intraoperative challenges and implement preventive strategies. While further

validation in larger cohorts is warranted, PAI measurement shows promise in optimizing surgical outcomes, enhancing patient care, and advancing our understanding of pancreatic disease management.

References

- Chen H, Fu N, Zhong J, Wang C, Xu Z, Wang W, Cheng D, Weng Y, Deng X, Shen B. Enhancement pattern of the pancreatic parenchyma predicts postpancreatectomy acute pancreatitis after pancreaticoduodenectomy. *European Radiology*. 2024 Jan;34(1):6-15.
- Maqueda Gonzalez R, Di Martino M, Galan Gonzalez I, Rodriguez Carnero P, Martin-Perez E. Development of a prediction model of pancreatic fistula after duodenopancreatectomy and soft pancreas by assessing the preoperative image. *Langenbeck's Archives of Surgery*. 2022 Sep;407(6):2363-72.
- Iseki M, Noda H, Watanabe F, Kato T, Endo Y, Aizawa H, Fukui T, Ichida K, Kakizawa N, Rikiyama T. A deep pancreas is a novel predictor of pancreatic fistula after pancreaticodu-

- odenectomy in patients with a nondilated main pancreatic duct. *Surgery*. 2021 Jun 1;169(6):1471-9.
4. Xingjun G, Feng Z, Meiwen Y, Jianxin J, Zheng H, Jun G, Tao H, Rui Z, Leida Z, Min W, Renyi Q. A score model based on pancreatic steatosis and fibrosis and pancreatic duct diameter to predict postoperative pancreatic fistula after Pancreatoduodenectomy. *BMC surgery*. 2019 Dec; 19:1-8.
 5. Maehira H, Iida H, Maekawa T, Yasukawa D, Mori H, Takebayashi K, Kaida S, Miyake T, Matsubara A, Tani M. Estimated functional remnant pancreatic volume predicts nonalcoholic fatty liver disease after pancreaticoduodenectomy: use of computed tomography attenuation value of the pancreas. *HPB*. 2021 May 1;23(5):802-11.
 6. Perikinchira RA, Rajan R, Gisuthan B, Jayasree L, Swasthik KS, Subramanian S, Antony AV. Role of Pancreatic Attenuation Index in Assessing Pancreatic Fat Content and Post-pancreatectomy Outcomes. *Indian Journal of Radiology and Imaging*. 2023 Nov 20.
 7. Gnanasekaran S, Durgesh S, Gurram R, Kalayarasan R, Pottakkat B, Rajeswari M, Srinivas BH, Ramesh A, Sahoo J. Do preoperative pancreatic computed tomography attenuation index and enhancement ratio predict pancreatic fistula after pancreaticoduodenectomy? *World Journal of Radiology*. 2022 Jun 6;14(6):165.
 8. Yang F, Windsor JA, Fu DL. Optimizing prediction models for pancreatic fistula after pancreatectomy: Current status and future perspectives. *World Journal of Gastroenterology*. 2024 Mar 3;30(10):1329.
 9. Van Rijssen LB, Van Huijgevoort NC, Coelen RJ, Tol JA, Haverkort EB, Nio CY, Busch OR, Besselink MG. Skeletal muscle quality is associated with worse survival after pancreaticoduodenectomy for periampullary, nonpancreatic cancer. *Annals of surgical oncology*. 2017 Jan; 24:272-80.
 10. Wang H, Jin J, Zhu F, Peng F, Wang M, Qin R. The ratio of abdominal depth to body mass index is a preoperative predictor of postoperative complications after laparoscopic pancreaticoduodenectomy: a retrospective propensity score-matched analysis. *Surgical Endoscopy*. 2021 Dec; 35:6472-80.
 11. Shibata S, Takahashi Y, Oyama H, Minegishi Y, Tanaka K. Incidence and clinical characteristics of hepatic steatosis following pancreatectomy. *The Showa University Journal of Medical Sciences*. 2024;36(1):25-35.